

PEER PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Liu, R., Rong, K. (2025). Can mnes achieve performance through digital business strategy in China's institutional environment? *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(5), e2023-0476. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250504x>

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Liu, R., Rong, K. (2025). Peer review report for: Can mnes achieve performance through digital business strategy in China's institutional environment? *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(5), e2023-0476. *Zenodo*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15122652>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

The first reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Artur Tavares Vilas Boas Ribeiro , Universidade de São Paulo, Faculdade de Economia, Administração e Contabilidade, São Paulo, SP, Brazil.

Fernanda Cahen , Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing, São Paulo, SP, Brazil

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

The first reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Author's Response

Dear professor:

We thank you and the reviewers very much for giving us an opportunity to revise the manuscript (ID: RAE-2023-0476.R1), and also appreciate much for the positive and constructive comments and suggestions on the manuscript. These comments are much vital, and the potential weaknesses pointed out by the reviewers are indeed the ones we once ignored. For improving the manuscript quality, we made a major revision and submitted the revised manuscripts and a table explaining changes with page number. Besides, main revisions with responses to your comments (revisions are highlighted in yellow and the comments are purple) were submitted as well. We tried our best to revise the manuscript according to these key comments, and now there is much progress over the previous version. Please find the revised version and the response letter, and we are looking forward to your kind consideration.

We express our great appreciation to you and the reviewers again. Looking forward to hearing from you.

Yours sincerely,

All authors

ROUND 2

Reviewer 2 Report

Reviewer: Artur Tavares Vilas Boas Ribeiro

Date review returned: 20-Sep-2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author:

Dear authors,

Thank you for submitting the revised version of your manuscript. It has significantly improved from the previous version. However, there are a few important revisions needed in this manuscript before it can be published.

First, the research question(s) is still too broad, and the research gap around it is very confusing. Three RQs create a need for a way more profound theorization, and the paper doesn't address them in the conclusion section. Which were the strategies (qualitative question, hard to be answered by your model)? How can MNEs improve (same comment for the RQ1)? When will they work? This really needs a revision. I think the authors should think about one RQ only with a more quantitative focus.

Second, there's a need for improved conceptual clarity during the hypothesis creation. This section contains several logical leaps that require a more thorough explanation. H1, for instance, talks about performance, but the paragraphs that compose it talk about partnerships, cloud computing, and many more items. H2 and H3 do this very well, and the authors should follow it (concrete examples and a clear logical path). Maybe the H1, by being too broad, could be built upon the others only, without additional layers of performance (cloud computing and more).

Thirdly, enhancing the theoretical aspects of the conclusion section could strengthen the paper. Beyond merely affirming and responding to recent inquiries, a more extensive theorization of the findings is advisable. The domains of organizational learning and digitalization present an excellent opportunity for an in-depth exploration.

Lastly, there are a few minor adjustments needed: the terms “digital strategies” and “digital transformation” appear to be used interchangeably; the tables are not correctly sequenced—for example, Table 4, which is mentioned on page 15 in the moderating effect test, seems to correspond to a different table.

Reviewer 3 Report

Reviewer: Fernanda Cahen

Date review returned: 24-Sep-2024

Recommendation: Major revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author:

The paper “Can multinational enterprises in China achieve performance through digital business strategy? The moderating effect of different institutional distance” explores a timely and exciting topic. However, in its current version, the paper has several issues that need attention before publication. I hope my comments will help the author(s) to clarify and improve the paper.

- 1. Title: I suggest the authors consider the title of the paper. It is long, with two phases and a question. The use of the word “different” doesn’t read well.*
- 2. Please, rewrite your abstract. It seems that you copied and pasted fragments of the main article. You use “these multinationals”. in the first and second phases of the abstract. That doesn’t make sense. The way it is, it is hard for the reader to understand the contributions of the paper. You bring the results in the abstract, but those findings mean? The abstract sets the tone for the rest of the paper. Make it clearer the paper’s objectives, method, and contributions.*
- 3. In your introduction section, the theoretical gaps need to be spelled out better. You present three research questions. However, you don’t present arguments that lead the reader to understand such questions. This issue is critical for you to convince the significance of this study. Please clarify in the introduction what is missing in the literature of IB, that justifies the analysis of these questions. You affirm that China is a “typical” emerging market. China is not “typical” – It’s not a democracy, has the second GDP in the world, the second biggest population, and lots of internet restrictions. The context matter. It is not only your research setting. ? What does this Chinese institutional context bring to the field/discussion of IB? In the 4th paragraph, you did a very good job stating the contributions of the paper.*
- 4. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development: Here is the section that you should spend more time improving. You jump into hypothesis development without giving the context of the literature you are working on. What is missing in the IB literature about digitalization that justifies this study on China? It feels that you state the hypotheses without an argumentative narrative. It is hard to follow how you, from your promises in the contributions (in the Introduction section), end up in your Hypotheses.*
- 5. I suggest the authors to separate the sections of Literature Review and Research Hypotheses and focus on more precise discussions for the hypothesis creation. Make sure that every hypothesis is truly grounded on the literature (in what is missing in the literature).*
- 6. Methodology: Again you affirm that China is a “typical” emerging market. China is not “typical”. The context matter and China is not only your research setting, but the way you present it in the methodology, your results would be the same in any emerging market. Please, pay attention to the coherence of your ideas and methodological steps. Most of the information is already there, but your writing and structure of the section is confusing. Please, re-organize the information on your variables and measurements. Complete Table 2 with the references you used to build your questionnaire. That helps to make it clear the operationalization of the variables.*

7. Results: I'm ok with the section.
8. Discussion and Implications: I liked this section.
9. The manuscript requires improvement in linguistic quality. Several sentences have grammatical errors and structural issues that hinder readability. Before resubmission, a thorough round of professional copyediting is recommended.
10. The paper has potential; good luck in the review process!!

Author's Response

dear reviewers:

Thanks much for your helpful and key comments concerning the manuscript titled "Can MNEs achieve performance through digital business strategy in china's institutional environment?". (ID: RAE-2023-0476.R2). These comments are valuable and much helpful for revising and improving the manuscript and are also instructional for our following researches. We made major revisions in the hope that we could receive your approval. The revised version of the manuscripts is submitted and the main revisions with responses to your comments are as follows (revisions are highlighted in yellow and the comments are purple). Please see the attachments.

Notes: All comments on grammar and communication have been revised in a unified way.

Reviewer: 2

Comments:

First, the research question(s) is still too broad, and the research gap around it is very confusing. Three RQs create a need for a way more profound theorization, and the paper doesn't address them in the conclusion section. Which were the strategies (qualitative question, hard to be answered by your model)? How can MNEs improve (same comment for the RQ1)? When will they work? This really needs a revision. I think the authors should think about one RQ only with a more quantitative focus.

Response: Thank you very much for your comments and suggestions. As you mentioned, we recognize that the research questions (RQs) in the paper were indeed too broad and needed greater focus. Based on your suggestions, we have refined our research question to focus on a single, more specific inquiry that can be effectively addressed through a quantitative model. This narrower focus is designed to be more precise, aligning closely with the current research gap and the subsequent hypotheses and contributions of the paper. By concentrating on one research question, we aim to provide a more focused and measurable exploration, one that can be rigorously tested and offer actionable insights for MNEs. The specific revisions are listed below for your checking, and we hope to receive your approval.

[INTRODUCTION

Given the competitive advantages that multinational enterprises (MNEs) possess in economies of scale, knowledge acquisition, and learning, research into corporate internationalization has flourished (Arzubiaga et al., 2021). The advancement of contemporary digital technologies has introduced innovative business models and opportunities, but have exacerbated the uncertainties and competition globally (Bresciani et al., 2021). Scholars have devoted significant effort to investigating the antecedents, outcomes, and mechanisms of influence on the international

performance of MNEs in the digital era (Bauweraerts et al., 2022). However, to date, much of the academic focus on the nuances of technology (Blichfeldt & Faullant, 2021). While these studies have enriched our understanding of the role of digital technologies in enhancing performance, they seem to overlook non-technical factors, especially strategic considerations. Indeed, strategy encompasses a holistic understanding of an organization's cognition, essence, and actions (Ukko et al., 2019). To comprehend internationalization strategies in the digital age, scholars suggest integrating digital strategies with business development strategies (Bharadwaj et al., 2013).

Existing research found that MNEs need to formulate sound business strategies to cope with the changing international market dynamics (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). Digital business strategy is regarded as a cohesive set of strategic plans and actions aimed at leveraging digital technologies to achieve business objectives, enhance competitiveness (Mithas, Tafti, and Mitchell, 2013). Nevertheless, MNEs often encounter challenges when customizing digital solutions according to local conditions (Mazé & Chailan, 2021), and its implementation effect may be closely related to the host country environment. At present, most of the research focuses on the implementation effect of digital business strategy in developed countries with advanced technology, perfect system and mature market, and very few studies focus on normal emerging markets constrained by relatively immature markets and infrastructure (Goldman et al., 2022). In contrast, China has a unique cultural background, complex regulatory environment, rapid development of digital technology, significant regional differences and rapidly changing consumer requirements, which brings more unique and severe challenges to the implementation of digital business strategy MNEs in China (Li et al., 2022). However, few studies have investigated the management practice and internal mechanism of MNEs operating in China in the transitional period to improve its performance through digital business strategy. Ignoring the uniqueness of implementing digital business strategy in different host countries may lead to insufficient understanding of the diversity of the global market and lack of guiding significance for the actual strategic decision-making of MNEs in China. In addition, most discussions on digital business strategy are still limited to theoretical framework or specific case studies (Pagani, 2013), and there is no empirical verification on the mechanism and boundary conditions of digital business strategy to promote the performance of multinational enterprises, especially how to improve the international performance in the complex institutional environment of the host country (Prashar & Hamid, 2022). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the specific mechanism and situational conditions for multinational enterprises operating in China to achieve performance improvement through digital business strategy.]

Second, there's a need for improved conceptual clarity during the hypothesis creation. This section contains several logical leaps that require a more thorough explanation. H1, for instance, talks about performance, but the paragraphs that compose it talk about partnerships, cloud computing, and many more items. H2 and H3 do this very well, and the authors should follow it (concrete examples and a clear logical path). Maybe the H1, by being too broad, could be built upon the others only, without additional layers of performance (cloud computing and more).

Response: Many thanks for your comments and suggestions. We recognize that the discussion in this section currently introduces several elements—such as partnerships, cloud computing, and performance—that may appear disconnected, leading to potential confusion. Upon further reflection, we agree that the broad scope of H1 could be narrowed to provide greater conceptual clarity and coherence. To address this, we will revise H1 to focus more specifically on the direct relationships between the key variables, ensuring a clearer, more logical progression. The specific revisions are listed below for your checking, and we hope to receive your approval.

[Digital business strategy and firm performance

Digital business strategy is devised and implemented through the leverage of digital resources to craft differentiated value (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). Reflecting on various perspectives of digital business strategy, we define digital managerial capability and digital operational capability as the primary aspects of digital business strategy. Managerial capability refers to the ability of managers to utilize digitalization in business strategy, employee mindset and skills, and the workplace. While operational capability denotes the enterprise's ability to integrate digitalization into its overall business processes and corporate strategy (Ukko et al., 2019).

First, digital managerial capability enhances the adaptability of MNEs in the host country market. As an organizational-level strategy, digital business strategy has a strong guiding effect on firm behavior (Bharadwaj et al., 2013), encouraging the enhancement of employee digital literacy and work efficiency through digital means, enabling them to better adapt to the labor demands and cultural background of the host country market. In China, MNEs' digital business strategies are often encouraged and supported by government policies. As a result, MNEs implementing digital business strategies can optimize their internal digital infrastructure, such as utilizing cloud computing services, internal social media platforms, and collaboration tools to ensure that employees can easily access company resources, enabling real-time communication and information sharing. This facilitates employees in subsidiaries located in different geographical regions to share business-related knowledge and best practices using digital infrastructure, thereby fully leveraging intellectual capital for company development and innovation (Chatterjee et al., 2023).

Second, digital operational capability enhances the optimization of business processes, improving production efficiency and reducing operational costs. In the host country market, MNEs face diverse supply chains and production processes, and digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics can help enterprises monitor and optimize these processes in real-time, thus improving overall operational efficiency. Through digital supply chain management, companies can reduce inventory, optimize production schedules, and more accurately forecast market demand, avoiding resource waste (Wedel & Kannan, 2016).

Third, the synergy between digital managerial capability and digital operational capability contributes to intelligent decision-making, improving a firm's responsiveness and decision-making efficiency. Through big data analytics and AI, MNEs can conduct in-depth analyses of market trends, consumer behavior, and competitive dynamics, making data-driven decisions (Parise, Guinan, and Kafka, 2016). MNEs can adjust their decisions related to product development, marketing, and resource allocation based on real-time data, thereby better adapting to the changes and demands in the host country market. For example, real-time digital business strategies enable MNEs to gain real-time insights into customer behavior, market trends, and competitive landscapes through vast databases and data mining techniques (Lamberton & Stephen, 2016). In particular, in the Chinese market, where consumer demand fluctuates greatly, digital business strategies help enterprises achieve dynamic adjustments, thus enhancing market responsiveness. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Digital business strategy has a positive impact on the performance of MNEs operating in China.]

Thirdly, enhancing the theoretical aspects of the conclusion section could strengthen the paper. Beyond merely affirming and responding to recent inquiries, a more extensive theorization of the findings is advisable. The domains of organizational learning and digitalization present an excellent opportunity for an in-depth exploration.

Response: Many thanks for your comments and suggestions. With your advice, we have expanded the discussion to more extensively theorize the implications of our findings, particularly in the domains of organizational learning and digitalization. The specific revisions are listed below for your checking, and we hope to receive your approval.

[Theoretical implications

This study makes a significant contribution to the literature. It shifts the research focus from digital technologies or singular functional strategies to a more inclusive and embedded digital business strategy, grounded in the literature of internationalization and organizational learning. With digital technologies enabling multinational corporations to transcend physical and cultural barriers, there has been an increasing research interest in digitalization and firm performance (Shuyan et al., 2023). While many firms are attempting digital business strategy, recent studies suggest that the enhancement of competitive advantage and success is not solely dependent on the technologies and services adopted (Prashar & Hamid, 2022). The integration of technology and business models is more likely to pave the way for MNEs to promote their operations globally (Knight & Liesch, 2016). This study provides detailed and novel insights into the digital business strategies of MNEs, responding to recent calls for a better integration of the uniqueness of internationalization strategies to explain firm performance (Bauweraerts et al., 2022). Moreover, China's hybrid institutional environment provides a unique context for addressing the research gap. As the world's second-largest economy and a driving force behind digital development, China presents a dynamic and complex institutional landscape where multinational corporations must navigate between strong formal regulations and informal norms (such as networks of relationships). The combination of institutional duality, rapid policy changes, and regional heterogeneity challenges traditional international business frameworks. By examining the mechanisms and boundary conditions of digital strategy implementation within this context, this study contributes to the development of international business literature and offers actionable insights for multinational companies operating in similarly complex and dynamic environments.

Subsequently, this study advances the literature on organizational learning by unveiling the mediating role between digital business strategies and performance outcomes. Previous research has scant attention to how digital business strategies translate their global influence into profitability. By investigating two distinct dimensions of organizational learning—exploitative learning and explorative learning—as mediators in the relationship between digital business strategy and performance, the research addresses this gap. The effectiveness of a digital business strategy is not solely contingent upon the strategy itself but also depends on two different organizational learning processes to refine and integrate knowledge and realize collaborative reconstruction (Zhang & Yang, 2021). This research responds to the call by Arzubiaga et al. (2021) for enriched dialogue and interaction between the fields of internationalization and organizational learning, deepening the understanding of organizational learning processes and outcomes within firms operating internationally.

Finally, the above research conclusions help to further understand the boundary conditions of digital business strategy by revealing the heterogeneous moderation of formal and informal institutional distance on the relationship between digital business strategy and organizational learning. Specifically, this research focuses on the dual boundary effects of institutional distance, which makes up for the deficiency that previous studies ignored its potential positive impact (Trąpczyński & Banalieva, 2016). This is consistent with the view of Li et al. (2020), that is, institutional distance has negative effects such as lack of legitimacy and information asymmetry, as well as positive effects such as institutional arbitrage and knowledge accumulation. Besides, we further reveal the differentiated moderating roles of formal and informal institutional distances, which goes beyond the traditional view that the two are homogeneous in the existing research. Formal institutions are more enduring and relatively stable, whereas informal institutions are more malleable and likely to be altered and leveraged, thus MNEs are more likely to exploit the integrative and reconfigurative potentials of digital business strategies, enhancing international performance through co-creation of institutions. Therefore, this study echoes previous literature by identifying the heterogeneity between formal and informal institutional distances (Liou et al., 2016).]

Lastly, there are a few minor adjustments needed: the terms “digital strategies” and “digital transformation” appear to be used interchangeably; the tables are not correctly sequenced—for example, Table 4, which is mentioned on page 15 in the moderating effect test, seems to correspond to a different table.

Response: Thank you for your valuable feedback on the submitted research paper. I appreciate your careful review and constructive suggestions. Based on your comments, I will make the following adjustments. First, clarification of terms (“Digital Strategies” and “Digital Transformation”). As you mentioned, the terms “digital strategies” and “digital transformation” were used interchangeably, which may cause confusion. I will revise the manuscript and unify the term “digital business strategy”. Second, table sequencing issue. I understand that the incorrect sequencing of tables has caused some confusion. Specifically, Table 4, referenced on page 15 in the moderating effect test, appears to correspond to a different table. I will carefully review the manuscript and ensure that all tables are correctly numbered and referenced in the text. The issue with Table 4 will be corrected, and I will verify that all subsequent tables are properly aligned with their references to avoid any discrepancies.

We appreciate you again for the comments and help on the manuscript with the hope that the revisions are valuable and meet the publication of RAE.

Reviewer: 3

Comments:

1. Title: I suggest the authors consider the title of the paper. It is long, with two phases and a question. The use of the word “different” doesn’t read well.

Response: Many thanks for your comments and the valuable feedback on the title’s clarity and length. We agree that the current title might be overly long and the use of the word “different” could potentially cause confusion. In line with the principle of conciseness and to enhance clarity, we have revised the title to “Can MNEs achieve performance through digital business strategy in China’s institutional environment?” This revision maintains the core focus of the paper while streamlining the structure for better readability. We believe this change better aligns with both academic conventions and the need for a more succinct presentation of the research’s central inquiry.

2. Please, rewrite your abstract. It seems that you copied and pasted fragments of the main article. You use “these multinationals”. in the first and second phases of the abstract. That doesn’t make sense. The way it is, it is hard for the reader to understand the contributions of the paper. You bring the results in the abstract, but those findings mean? The abstract sets the tone for the rest of the paper. Make it clearer the paper’s objectives, method, and contributions.

Thank you for your valuable feedback on our abstract. We appreciate your detailed observations and agree that the current version could benefit from more clarity and focus. Based on your comments, we revised the abstract to better communicate the objectives, methods, and contributions of our paper. Please check the specific revisions in introduction and we hope to receive your approval.

[ABSTRACT

There is limited knowledge about how and when multinational enterprises (MNEs) operating in China can achieve performance through digital business strategy. This study addresses this gap by exploring the mechanisms through which digital business strategy affect enterprise performance from the perspective of organizational learning. Using hierarchical regression analysis and two-stage data from 305 MNEs, the theoretical model was empirically tested. The results showed that implementing digital business strategy significantly enhances MNEs’

performance, with exploitative and explorative learning serving as key mediators in this process. The formal institutional distance negatively moderates the relationship between digital business strategy and both types of learning, while informal institutional distance positively moderates this relationship. Consequently, MNEs should strive to mitigate the potential adverse effects of highly coercive formal institutional environments and leverage the flexible and dynamic nature of informal institutional environments to maximize the proactive role of digital business strategy in enhancing performance. This study contributes to the literature on digital business strategy and offers practical insights for MNEs in designing and implementing effective digital strategy.]

3. In your introduction section, the theoretical gaps need to be spelled out better. You present three research questions. However, you don't present arguments that lead the reader to understand such questions. This issue is critical for you to convince the significance of this study. Please clarify in the introduction what is missing in the literature of IB, that justifies the analysis of these questions. You affirm that China is a "typical" emerging market. China is not "typical" – It's not a democracy, has the second GDP in the world, the second biggest population, and lots of internet restrictions. The context matter. It is not only your research setting. ? What does this Chinese institutional context bring to the field/discussion of IB? In the 4th paragraph, you did a very good job stating the contributions of the paper.

Response: Thanks for your suggestions. We revised the introduction to more clearly identify the gaps in the existing literature on International Business and explain why these gaps necessitate the exploration of the research questions posed in this study. Regarding the characterization of China as a "typical" emerging market, we agree that this characterization oversimplifies the unique context of China. We will remove this description and instead focus on the rapid digitalization of China, coupled with an institutional environment that is still evolving. This creates a distinctive setting for business operations, with both opportunities and challenges stemming from the country's technological advancement alongside its regulatory and governance issues. The gap this study addresses lies in understanding how firms navigate this complex environment, where digital transformation is accelerating but institutional frameworks are not yet fully aligned with global norms. This revision will also better connect the research questions to the institutional context, demonstrating how the rapid digitalization and regulatory uncertainties in China create unique challenges for international business that are underexplored in current literature. By examining the intersection of digital development and institutional imperfections, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of IB in emerging markets, particularly in the context of China. This will highlight the significance of the institutional environment as a critical factor influencing business behavior and strategy in such settings.

[INTRODUCTION

Given the competitive advantages that multinational enterprises (MNEs) possess in economies of scale, knowledge acquisition, and learning, research into corporate internationalization has flourished (Arzubiaga et al., 2021). The advancement of contemporary digital technologies has introduced innovative business models and opportunities, but have exacerbated the uncertainties and competition globally (Bresciani et al., 2021). Scholars have devoted significant effort to investigating the antecedents, outcomes, and mechanisms of influence on the international performance of MNEs in the digital era (Bauweraerts et al., 2022). However, to date, much of the academic focus on the nuances of technology.(Blichfeldt & Faullant, 2021). While these studies have enriched our understanding of the role of digital technologies in enhancing performance, they seem to overlook non-technical factors, especially strategic considerations. Indeed, strategy encompasses a holistic understanding of an organization's cognition, essence, and actions (Ukko et al., 2019). To comprehend internationalization strategies in the digital age, scholars suggest integrating digital strategies with business development strategies (Bharadwaj et al., 2013).

Existing research found that MNEs need to formulate sound business strategies to cope with the changing international market dynamics (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). Digital business strategy is regarded as a cohesive set of strategic plans and actions aimed at leveraging digital technologies to achieve business objectives, enhance competitiveness (Mithas, Tafti, and Mitchell, 2013). Nevertheless, MNEs often encounter challenges when customizing digital solutions according to local conditions (Mazé & Chailan, 2021), and its implementation effect may be closely related to the host country environment. At present, most of the research focuses on the implementation effect of digital business strategy in developed countries with advanced technology, perfect system and mature market, and very few studies focus on normal emerging markets constrained by relatively immature markets and infrastructure (Goldman et al., 2022). In contrast, China has a unique cultural background, complex regulatory environment, rapid development of digital technology, significant regional differences and rapidly changing consumer requirements, which brings more unique and severe challenges to the implementation of digital business strategy MNEs in China (Li et al., 2022). However, few studies have investigated the management practice and internal mechanism of MNEs operating in China in the transitional period to improve its performance through digital business strategy. Ignoring the uniqueness of implementing digital business strategy in different host countries may lead to insufficient understanding of the diversity of the global market and lack of guiding significance for the actual strategic decision-making of MNEs in China. In addition, most discussions on digital business strategy are still limited to theoretical framework or specific case studies (Pagani, 2013), and there is no empirical verification on the mechanism and boundary conditions of digital business strategy to promote the performance of multinational enterprises, especially how to improve the international performance in the complex institutional environment of the host country (Prashar & Hamid, 2022). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the specific mechanism and situational conditions for multinational enterprises operating in China to achieve performance improvement through digital business strategy.

Despite significant advancements in research on digital business strategy and international performance (Chi et al., 2018), there remains a substantial gap in understanding how certain MNEs successfully leverage digital business strategies while others do not. The process of acquiring, integrating, and reconfiguring valuable knowledge within and across the boundaries of multinational corporations is frequent in the internationalization process (Surdu & Narula, 2021). Therefore, the unpredictability of outcomes from digital business strategies often manifests as a function of knowledge and organizational learning processes (Arzubiaga et al., 2021; Chung et al., 2019). Exploitative and explorative learning signify crucial capabilities in the process of internationalization (Larkin, 2020). Therefore, this study aims to bridge this gap by positing that the digital business strategy of MNEs constitutes an organizational learning process dependent on ambidextrous learning (i.e., exploitative and explorative learning) to identify and exploit new product/market opportunities, thereby enhancing international performance. Ambidextrous learning aims to facilitate the interaction of internationalizing firms with the novel environments of host countries (Arzubiaga et al., 2021). Undoubtedly, the institutional environment during the process of internationalization represents a critical factor influencing the strategic choices and performance of multinational corporations (Peng, 2003; Surdu & Narula, 2021). In this study, we introduce formal and informal institutional distance as moderating variables to elucidate how varying degrees of institutional disparities influence the impact of digital business strategies on performance. Formal institutional distance refers to differences in laws and regulations, characterized by enforceability. Firms often passively adapt through sacrificing efficiency and cost minimization to gain legitimacy (Zhang & Yang, 2021), thereby undermining the potential value of digital business strategies. In contrast, informal institutional distance reflects differences in norms and cognition (Yang et al., 2012), characterized by malleability and dynamism. Thus, this study integrates the concepts of exploitative and explorative learning based on organizational learning theory and institutional theory (Schildt, Maula, & Keil, 2005), to gain a nuanced understanding of the relationship between digital business strategies and firm performance, especially within the context of varying institutional distances in host countries.

This study makes several important contributions to the international business and organizational learning literatures. First, this study transcends mere technical or functional strategy considerations, offering a nuanced understanding of how the integration strategies of digital technologies and business models can act as catalysts for enhancing the performance of multinational corporations in China (Knight & Liesch, 2016; Prashar & Hamid, 2022). Second, the study advances the literature on organizational learning by revealing the mediating role of exploitative and explorative learning between digital business strategies and performance, which addresses scholars' calls for a deeper understanding of the antecedents, processes, and outcomes of organizational learning in an international context (Chung et al., 2019; Arzubiaga et al., 2021). Third, this research seeks to clarify the boundary conditions under which digital business strategies enhance or fail to improve the performance of these multinational corporations, namely institutional distance. Incorporating the moderating variable of institutional distance supports the logic and impact mechanisms of both formal and informal institutional distances' heterogeneity while responding to calls for research emphasizing the context-specific nature of the relationship between internationalization and performance (Bauweraerts et al., 2022). Our findings also offer practical strategic guidance for MNEs operating in China, inspiring them on how to maximize the advantages of digital business strategies to enhance international performance.]

4. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development: Here is the section that you should spend more time improving. You jump into hypothesis development without giving the context of the literature you are working on. What is missing in the IB literature about digitalization that justifies this study on China? It feels that you state the hypotheses without an argumentative narrative. It is hard to follow how you, from your promises in the contributions (in the Introduction section), end up in your Hypotheses.

5. I suggest the authors to separate the sections of Literature Review and Research Hypotheses and focus on more precise discussions for the hypothesis creation. Make sure that every hypothesis is truly grounded on the literature (in what is missing in the literature).

Response: We sincerely appreciate your constructive feedback on our manuscript, particularly regarding the Literature Review and Hypotheses Development section. We recognize that the connection between the existing literature and the hypotheses we proposed requires clearer elaboration and more precise justification. In light of your comments, we added the Literature Review section and revised the Hypotheses Development section to better delineate the gaps in the existing literature on digitalization in International Business (IB), particularly in the context of China, and to clarify how our hypotheses emerge from these gaps. Please check the specific revisions below and we hope to receive your approval.

[LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital business strategy

Digital business strategy emphasizes the integration of digital technologies with business strategies to address the challenges of digitalization arising from innovation and technology (Ukko et al., 2019), and has become a critical management priority for organizations (Holopainen et al., 2023). This study follows the framework proposed by Bharadwaj et al. (2013), defining digital business strategy as the organizational strategy formulated and executed to create differentiated value through the utilization of digital resources. This suggests that digital business strategy should not be viewed merely as a functional-level strategy, but as “a clear, broad, and organization-wide strategy.” Unlike traditional business strategies, firms implementing a digital business strategy emphasize appropriate investment in digital infrastructure and technologies to manage risks and uncertainties in international markets (Chi et al., 2022), thereby leveraging their strengths in complex and diverse host-country environments. This requires companies to simultaneously develop new organizational capabilities through learning as they expand their business.

Digital business strategy and firm performance

First, there is a clear gap in the discussion regarding the significance of digital strategy. Most existing research primarily focuses on technical details (Opazo-Basáez, Vendrell-Herrero, & Bustinza, 2022), without integrating digital technologies with strategy. Empirical evidence shows that digital technologies play a crucial role in business model innovation, having a positive impact on both performance and customer satisfaction (Facin et al., 2023). While these studies enhance our understanding of the role of digital technologies in improving performance, they appear to overlook non-technical factors, particularly strategic considerations.

As the research has evolved, scholars have increasingly focused on the core idea of “integration of digital technologies and business strategy,” conducting a series of studies from both strategic and technological perspectives. However, no consensus has been reached. At the strategic level, there is debate regarding the relationship between digital business strategy and firm performance. Some studies, such as those by Ukko et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2020), suggest that the direct effect of digital business strategy on performance is not significant and that mediating effects (e.g., IT capabilities) or moderating mechanisms (e.g., sustainability strategies) should be considered. In contrast, studies by Chi et al. (2022) and Holopainen et al. (2023) found that digital business strategy has a significant positive direct effect on performance. At the technological level, research has focused on the impact of digital technologies, such as business process digitization and digital business intensity (Nwankpa and Datta, 2017), on firm performance, confirming a significant positive effect. These findings suggest that the direct effects of digital business strategy on firm performance merit further investigation, and the neglect of contextual factors may be an important reason for the differing results.

Third, although existing research has provided an empirical foundation for further exploration, current process paths are primarily derived from case studies and literature analysis, with limited large-sample empirical testing. The few empirical studies that do exist have mainly focused on developed countries such as the United States, Germany, and Sweden, with insufficient exploration of emerging markets like China, where digital technology is rapidly developing and regulatory environments are stringent. Mies et al. (2024) conducted a cluster analysis using a global sample of firms (including those from Germany, Sweden, etc.), identifying four basic types of digital business strategies and evaluating their impact on company performance, which contributes to a better understanding of new business strategy concepts in the context of digitalization. Amarilli et al. (2023) explored the co-evolution of digital business strategies and organizational socio-technical systems through case studies and system dynamics, revealing the important roles of factors such as executive commitment and communication structures. Nwankpa and Datta (2017), based on empirical data collected from Chief Information Officers in U.S. companies, found that while IT capabilities positively affect organizational performance, the strength of this relationship may vary across different levels of digital business strategies. These findings suggest that the questions of “whether” and “how” digital business strategies can enhance firm performance have not yet been systematically studied in the existing literature.

HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Digital business strategy and firm performance

Digital business strategy is devised and implemented through the leverage of digital resources to craft differentiated value (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). Reflecting on various perspectives of digital business strategy, we define digital managerial capability and digital operational capability as the primary aspects of digital business strategy. Managerial capability refers to the ability of managers to utilize digitalization in business strategy, employee mindset and skills, and the workplace. While operational capability denotes the enterprise’s ability to integrate digitalization into its overall business processes and corporate strategy (Ukko et al., 2019).

First, digital managerial capability enhances the adaptability of MNEs in the host country market. As an organizational-level strategy, digital business strategy has a strong guiding effect on firm behavior (Bharadwaj et al., 2013), encouraging the enhancement of employee digital literacy and work efficiency through digital means, enabling them to better adapt to the labor demands and cultural background of the host country market. In China, MNEs' digital business strategies are often encouraged and supported by government policies. As a result, MNEs implementing digital business strategies can optimize their internal digital infrastructure, such as utilizing cloud computing services, internal social media platforms, and collaboration tools to ensure that employees can easily access company resources, enabling real-time communication and information sharing. This facilitates employees in subsidiaries located in different geographical regions to share business-related knowledge and best practices using digital infrastructure, thereby fully leveraging intellectual capital for company development and innovation (Chatterjee et al., 2023).

Second, digital operational capability enhances the optimization of business processes, improving production efficiency and reducing operational costs. In the host country market, MNEs face diverse supply chains and production processes, and digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics can help enterprises monitor and optimize these processes in real-time, thus improving overall operational efficiency. Through digital supply chain management, companies can reduce inventory, optimize production schedules, and more accurately forecast market demand, avoiding resource waste (Wedel & Kannan, 2016).

Third, the synergy between digital managerial capability and digital operational capability contributes to intelligent decision-making, improving a firm's responsiveness and decision-making efficiency. Through big data analytics and AI, MNEs can conduct in-depth analyses of market trends, consumer behavior, and competitive dynamics, making data-driven decisions (Parise, Guinan, and Kafka, 2016). MNEs can adjust their decisions related to product development, marketing, and resource allocation based on real-time data, thereby better adapting to the changes and demands in the host country market. For example, real-time digital business strategies enable MNEs to gain real-time insights into customer behavior, market trends, and competitive landscapes through vast databases and data mining techniques (Lamberton & Stephen, 2016). In particular, in the Chinese market, where consumer demand fluctuates greatly, digital business strategies help enterprises achieve dynamic adjustments, thus enhancing market responsiveness. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Digital business strategy has a positive impact on the performance of MNEs operating in China.

The mediating effect of exploitative and explorative learning

As a concrete manifestation of globalization, MNEs possess the advantage of a "knowledge bundle," enabling them to acquire a wide array of information and new knowledge from multiple sources to innovate and gain competitive edge (Larkin, 2020; Bauweraerts et al., 2022). Research indicates that organizational learning, which involves the acquisition and utilization of knowledge, is a key driver influencing organizational performance (Arzubiaga et al., 2021). Organizational learning refers to the pursuit of and exploitative and explorative learning, focusing on how organizations acquire, process, store, and apply knowledge to improve their performance and adaptability (March, 1991). In the context of implementing digital business strategy, organizational learning underpins the enhanced synergistic capabilities of MNEs, a lack of learning capacity results in the ineffective allocation of organizational resources (Bahar et al., 2021). Thus, this study posits that the digital business strategy of MNEs relies on the process of acquiring and utilizing new knowledge and market opportunities through organizational learning to enhance their international performance.

Drawing on organizational learning theory, exploitative learning necessitates a reduction in variation and an increase in efficiency. It emphasizes the improvement and optimization of existing knowledge, skills, and resources by MNEs (March, 1991). Digital business strategies reveal bottlenecks and inefficiencies within business processes, providing clearer insights for optimizing these processes (Chen et al., 2021). For example, IKEA's promotion of its digital home design tools in China (eg, online planning tools and AR) enhances the shopping experience for customers and provide IKEA with a wealth of user behavior data, aiding the company in better understanding the needs of the Chinese market, thereby allowing for rapid iteration and innovation. Actually, digital business strategies also facilitate the accumulation and flow of knowledge and experience within MNEs through digital platforms, internal networks, and digital collaboration tools, laying the foundation for exploitative learning in organizing, disseminating, and utilizing collective knowledge (Atuahene-Gima & Murray, 2007). Through accessible interactive interfaces and communication tools, digital business strategies help enterprises operating in China to establish cross-border cooperative networks, facilitating business expansion and optimal resource allocation (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). The collaboration (digital ecosystem) between Microsoft and Huawei in the fields of cloud computing and artificial intelligence is another exemplary case. We therefore posited that:

H2a: Digital business strategy has a positive impact on the exploitative learning of MNEs operating in China, thus promoting performance.

In contrast, explorative learning emphasizes the pursuit of new knowledge and transformation (March, 1991). Digital business strategies inherently support this learning model. On one hand, digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data analytics assist MNEs operating in China in filtering high-value knowledge and deeply mining critical information about local user purchasing behavior, market trends, and competitive dynamics (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). Furthermore, data processing and analysis offer a broader and more in-depth understanding of consumer behavior, market trends, and the optimization of decision-making processes (Mithas, Tafti, & Mitchell, 2013). Explorative learning, built upon digital business strategies, aids multinational corporations in devising product and service solutions that meet the unique market demands of local contexts (Surdu & Narula, 2021). For instance, Tesla established its first Gigafactory in Shanghai, China (Gigafactory 3), and collected a large amount of consumer data in real time through Over-The-Air (OTA) technology to help it carry out targeted technological improvement and localized R&D innovation. On the other hand, establishing partnerships with local digital agencies provides multinational companies with the resource conditions for explorative learning (Blichfeldt & Faullant, 2021). By collaborating with local technology firms, MNEs can not only gain deep insights into grassroots markets but also develop innovative digital solutions tailored to local market needs and more accurately understand the subtle differences of Chinese digital consumers. For example, Procter & Gamble (P&G) has gained a broad user base, a mature logistics network and a wealth of digital marketing platforms and tools by establishing partnerships with China's e-commerce giants Alibaba and JD.COM, which is conducive to P&G's brand promotion in China market. Therefore, we propose the hypothesis:

H2b: Digital business strategy has a positive impact on the explorative learning of MNEs operating in China, thus promoting performance.

The moderating role of the institutional distance

Peng (2003) highlighted that institutional distance, reflecting differences in the institutional environments between countries, significantly influences the strategic choices and performance of multinational corporations during internationalization. To deeply analyze the impact of digital business strategies on international performance in different institutional environments, this study characterizes the institutional setting of MNEs'

operational locales through formal and informal institutional distances. Formal institutional distance refers to differences in laws, regulations, enforcement, arbitration, and regulatory intensity between the home and host countries. Informal institutional distance is attributed to differences in values, beliefs, customs, traditions, and behavioral codes between the home and host countries (Aguilera-Caracuel et al., 2013).

Formal institutions are characterized by coerciveness and asymmetric power, displaying greater durability, relative stability, and resistance to change or influence (Aguilera-Caracuel et al., 2013). Against the backdrop of formal institutional distance, firms are more likely to passively adapt to institutional differences at the expense of low costs and high efficiency. Consequently, a significant formal institutional distance presents MNEs with the liability of foreignness, making it challenging to achieve operational legitimacy in host countries and increasing the obstacles to organizational learning through digital business strategies. A lack of legitimacy implies a deficiency in social support and resources from local stakeholders due to low recognition (Delmas & Montes-Sancho, 2011). Therefore, when considering social acceptability, multinational corporations are concerned about unfamiliar aspects of home country laws, regulations, and practices to avoid misconduct in host countries. On one hand, a greater formal distance leads to increased uncertainty in legal environments, administrative procedures, and tax policies encountered by MNEs in host countries, hindering the implementation of digital business strategies (Yang et al., 2012). As the formal institutional distance between countries widens, MNEs often need to spend more time and resources adapting to local legal requirements, and may even need to redesign their digital business strategies to comply with local regulations. This leads to increased costs of information gathering and difficulty in resource acquisition, thereby impeding the efficiency of knowledge coordination, integration, transformation, and utilization, which is unfavorable for exploitative learning (Zhang & Yang, 2021). On the other hand, in environments with significant formal institutional distance, MNEs may struggle to effectively transfer knowledge accumulated in their home countries to host countries, thereby obstructing the learning processes of MNEs in host countries. This leads to the following hypothesis:

H3a: The formal institutional distance has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between digital business strategy and exploitative learning.

The degree of formal institutional differences poses challenges to the explorative learning processes of MNCs aimed at developing new knowledge in host country markets. On one hand, the distance in formal institutions increases market ambiguity, hindering MNCs' ability to understand the behavior of local consumers and interpret market information in the host country. As the distance grows, MNCs may become uncertain about how host country regulations and laws affect economic transactions (Luo, 2005), struggle to assess the market behavior of local channel members, and therefore may lack confidence in interpreting and evaluating market information as well as predicting future market trends in the host country. Such market ambiguities make it difficult for MNCs to engage in explorative learning through digital business strategies, to develop new products or services that align with local consumer preferences. On the other hand, organizational learning theory suggests that explorative learning is crucial for organizations to adapt to new environments and address uncertainties (March, 1991). However, in host countries where there is a significant distance in formal institutions, the differences in formal institutions and legal risks faced by MNCs may increase the costs and risks associated with learning, dampening their enthusiasm for engaging in explorative learning. For example, host countries often impose stringent reviews and restrictions on acquisitions by Chinese companies in sensitive industries and technologies for strict intellectual property protection. Therefore, we propose the hypothesis:

H3b: The formal institutional distance has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between digital business strategy and explorative learning.

Informal institutions refer to the unwritten norms, tacit rules, social values, behavioral standards, and cultural aspects present within social groups, organizational bodies, or governmental agencies (Zhang & Yang, 2021). These unwritten regulations and cultural knowledge resources are largely embedded within the organizational fabric of local businesses in host countries, exerting significant influence on economic behaviors (Aguilera-Caracuel et al., 2013). It is evident that, in comparison to formal institutions, informal institutions possess greater dynamism and malleability, allowing for continuous evolution. Consequently, businesses no longer passively face differences in informal institutions but tend to leverage their agency, reshaping institutions according to their unique characteristics and interests. As the distance of informal institutions increases, international business management becomes more complex, rendering traditional business strategies inadequate. In contrast, digital business strategies enable multinational corporations to utilize digital platforms and tools to establish cross-cultural networks of trust and communication with local partners, facilitating rapid integration into local markets and the acquisition of local business standards and practices. Furthermore, the partnership sharing mechanisms established by digital business strategies are advantageous for multinational corporations to solve problems and improve processes using existing knowledge, promoting an exploitative learning process for internal integration and collaboration (Park and Luo, 2001). Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4a: The informal institutional distance has a positive moderating effect on the relationship between digital business strategy and exploitative learning.

Generally speaking, host countries with a high distance in informal institutions tend to contain more diversified and heterogeneous resources, providing a fertile environment for explorative learning. On one hand, the environment of high distance in informal institutions stimulates the enthusiasm and subjective initiative of MNEs (Zhang & Yang, 2021), compelling them to utilize digital business strategies for the efficient coordination and integration of knowledge and technology with host country firms, thereby acquiring a wealth of diverse knowledge. Such diversified knowledge enables firms to better address new challenges, try new methods and experimental strategies, thus fostering explorative learning (Arzubiaga et al., 2021). Explorative learning, which deviates from a firm's original technological trajectory, carries certain risks but can help firms fully leverage the advantages of heterogeneous knowledge (March, 1991). Therefore, a higher distance in informal institutions motivates companies to explore new fields, while also providing them with sufficient foundational knowledge to support these explorations, ultimately leading to more innovative MNEs. On the other hand, host countries with a greater distance in informal institutions may present more opportunities and potential benefits (Gao et al., 2022). The undeveloped nature of the market offers more space for MNEs to explore and develop new business models, market positioning, and product innovations. In this context, digital business strategies can provide a quicker, more flexible response, promoting effective explorative learning to meet the needs of consumers under different cultures and values. Therefore, we propose the hypothesis:

H4b: The informal institutional distance has a positive moderating effect on the relationship between digital business strategy and explorative learning.]

Methodology: Again you affirm that China is a “typical” emerging market. China is not “typical”. The context matter and China is not only your research setting, but the way you present it in the methodology, your results would be the same in any emerging market. Please, pay attention to the coherence of your ideas and methodological steps. Most of the information is already there, but your writing and structure of the section is confusing. Please, re-organize the information on your variables and measurements. Complete Table 2 with the references you used to build your questionnaire. That helps to make it clear the operationalization of the variables.

Response: Thank you for your valuable feedback. As you have pointed out, China is not a “typical” emerging market. We have carefully reconsidered the methodology section and have removed the previous characterization of China as such. We fully acknowledge that China, as the world’s second-largest economy and a key driver of digitalization, presents a dynamic and complex institutional environment. Multinational corporations operating in China navigate a unique blend of strong formal regulations and informal norms, such as guanxi (relationship networks). The combination of institutional duality, rapid policy shifts, and regional heterogeneity poses significant challenges to traditional international business (IB) frameworks. This study specifically investigates how digital strategy implementation unfolds in this distinctive context, examining its mechanisms and boundary conditions. We believe this approach contributes to the advancement of IB literature and provides actionable insights for multinational companies operating in similarly complex and dynamic environments. According to your suggestions, we have reorganized the methodology section for better clarity and coherence. Additionally, we have updated Table 2 to include the references used to operationalize the variables, which we hope will further clarify their measurement and conceptualization. Please check the specific revisions below and we hope to receive your approval.

[METHODS

Data collection and sample

Representative data from MNEs operating in China provides valuable insights into the practical experience and impact of digital business strategy across various industries and markets. This data also offers cross-cultural experiences and valuable lessons for global multinational corporations. In this study, we gathered data from MNEs operating in China through two waves of surveys conducted between September 2022 and September 2023. The respondents primarily represented firms from the United States, Russia, and other regions, spanning industries such as manufacturing, construction, and finance.

To ensure reliability, we targeted middle and senior managers, including CEOs and senior executives, who possess a comprehensive understanding of their company’s operations. For data collection, we partnered with Credamo, a mature and reputable online survey organization in China, to help distribute the questionnaires. The survey design included sections on the survey’s purpose, the research institution, basic company information, scale items, and acknowledgments. The survey organization was tasked with distributing the questionnaire to a random sample of MNEs operating in China, with compensation based on the number of questionnaires completed. Since the data was collected via a self-administered questionnaire, response biases could occur. To minimize this, we offered a small incentive (50 yuan) embedded in the questionnaire’s link to encourage truthful responses. In line with ethical principles, we assured participants that their responses would be used solely for academic purposes and that their information would be kept confidential.

The survey was conducted in two stages. In the first wave, managers completed scales on digital business strategy, institutional distance, and organizational learning, while also providing information on control variables. A total of 412 questionnaires were distributed, yielding 357 valid responses. Questionnaires were excluded if answers were incomplete, showed patterns of identical responses (eight or more in a row), or exhibited signs of significant response bias. We conducted long-term follow-up surveys and interviews with business managers/CEOs. From these interactions, we learned that most companies typically spent at least a year developing their digital strategies before seeing measurable results. Based on this timeline, the second wave of data collection began in September 2023. In this wave, 357 questionnaires were distributed, resulting in 305 valid responses (see Table 1).]

Table 1. Scale items, factor, reliability and validity analysis

Digital business strategy (DBS); Cronbach's α = 0.848; CR = 0.887; AVE = 0.569		
DBS1	<i>In China, our firm is familiar with the development and use of digital technology</i>	0.811
DBS2	<i>In China, our firm has a clear vision of using digital technology in the future</i>	0.716
DBS3	<i>In China, our firm supports the application of digital technology in various business fields</i>	0.714
DBS4	<i>In China, using digital technology in internal processes has become an important part of our business</i>	0.769
DBS5	<i>In China, we are used to digital technology in our business</i>	0.750
DBS6	<i>In China, digital technology has improved our business operation</i>	0.762

Source: Ukko, J., Nasiri, M., Saunila, M., & Rantala, T. (2019). Sustainability strategy as a moderator in the relationship between digital business strategy and financial performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 236, 117626.

Exploitative learning (EIL); Cronbach's α = 0.722; CR = 0.843; AVE = 0.643		
EIL1	<i>We search for the usual and generally proven methods and solutions in our marketplace</i>	0.796
EIL2	<i>Our aim was to search for information to refine common methods and ideas in solving problems in the project</i>	0.783
EIL3	<i>Our aim was to search for ideas and information that we can implement well to ensure productivity rather than those ideas that could lead to implementation mistakes in the project and in the marketplace</i>	0.826

Explorative learning (ERL); Cronbach's α = 0.798; CR = 0.909; AVE = 0.769		
ERL1	<i>Our aim was to acquire knowledge to develop a project that led us into new areas of learning such as new markets and technological areas</i>	0.884
ERL2	<i>We collect novel information and ideas that go beyond our current market and business opportunity experiences</i>	0.875
ERL3	<i>Our aim was to collect new information that forced us to learn new things in the product development project</i>	0.873

Source: Atuahene-Gima, K., & Murray, J. (2007). Exploratory and exploitative learning in new product development: A social capital perspective on new technology ventures in China. *Journal of International Marketing*, 15(2), 1–29.

Firm performance (FP); Cronbach's α = 0.873; CR = 0.905; AVE = 0.614		
FP1	<i>With digital business strategy, our sales have improved</i>	0.777
FP2	<i>With digital business strategy, our profitability has improved</i>	0.757
FP3	<i>With digital business strategy, our customer retention rate has improved</i>	0.853
FP4	<i>With digital business strategy, our market share has increased</i>	0.779
FP5	<i>With digital business strategy, our customers respond more favourably to our new products/services than before</i>	0.737
FP6	<i>With digital business strategy, we introduce new products or services to the market more quickly than before</i>	0.795

Source: Perdana, A., Lee, H., Koh, S., & Arisandi, D. (2022). Data analytics in small and mid-size enterprises: Enablers and inhibitors for business value and firm performance. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 44: 100547.

Formal institutional distance (FID); Cronbach's α = 0.878; CR = 0.911; AVE = 0.672

FID1	<i>The enforcement of commercial laws and regulations is more standardized in China</i>	0.850
FID2	<i>Arbitration is more fair in China</i>	0.809
FID3	<i>Dispute settlement is more effective in China</i>	0.805
FID4	<i>Intellectual property protection is stronger in China</i>	0.829
FID5	<i>Government agencies have stronger supervision over channels in China</i>	0.805

Informal institutional distance (IID); Cronbach's α = 0.886; CR = 0.916; AVE = 0.686

IID1	<i>The overall cooperation between buyers is closer in China</i>	0.810
IID2	<i>Trust between companies is generally higher in China</i>	0.887
IID3	<i>The supervision of relevant industry associations is stronger in China</i>	0.803
IID4	<i>The quality of products or services of the whole industry is higher in China</i>	0.811
IID5	<i>Buyers' behavior is more standardized in China</i>	0.830

Source: Yang, Z., Su, C., & Fam, K. S. (2012). Dealing with institutional distances in international marketing channels: Governance strategies that engender legitimacy and efficiency. *Journal of Marketing*, 76(3), 41-55.

Organizational memory level (OML); Cronbach's α = 0.708; CR = 0.824; AVE = 0.610

OML1	<i>Members have a lot of knowledge concerning the digital business strategy implemented by the firm</i>	0.758
OML2	<i>Members have a lot of experience concerning the digital business strategy implemented by the firm</i>	0.827
OML3	<i>Members are very familiar with the digital business strategy implemented by the firm</i>	0.757

Organizational memory dispersion (OMD); Cronbach's α = 0.776; CR = 0.873; AVE = 0.696

OMD1	<i>Members have a common understanding of the overall thinking of digital business strategy</i>	0.765
OMD2	<i>Members have a consensus on the ultimate goal of digital business strategy</i>	0.872
OMD3	<i>Members have a consensus on the specific measures of digital business strategy</i>	0.863

Source: Moorman, C., & Miner, A. (1997). The impact of organizational memory on new product performance and creativity. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34(1), 91-106.

Market turbulence (MT); Cronbach's α = 0.864; CR = 0.898; AVE = 0.596

MT1	<i>In our kind of business, customers' product preferences change quite a bit over time</i>	0.879
MT2	<i>Our customers tend to look for new product all the time</i>	0.734
MT3	<i>Sometimes our customers are very price-sensitive, but on other occasions</i>	0.757
MT4	<i>We are witnessing demand for our products and services from customers who never bought them before</i>	0.754
MT5	<i>New customers tend to have product-related needs that are different from those of our existing customers</i>	0.777
MT6	<i>We cater to many of the same customers that we used to in the past</i>	0.721

<i>Technological turbulence (TT); Cronbach's α = 0.856; CR = 0.897; AVE = 0.638</i>		
TT1	<i>The technology in our industry is changing rapidly</i>	0.818
TT2	<i>Technological changes provide big opportunities in our industry</i>	0.805
TT3	<i>It is very difficult to forecast where the technology in our industry will be in the next 2 to 3 years</i>	0.881
TT4	<i>A large number of new product ideas have been made possible through technological breakthroughs in our industry</i>	0.717
TT5	<i>Technological developments in our industry are rather minor</i>	0.765

Source: Jaworski, B., & Kohli, A. (1993). Market orientation: Antecedents and consequences. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(3), 53–70.

Notes: N = 305; Construct reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE). Source: Elaborated by authors.

7. Results: I'm ok with the section.

8. Discussion and Implications: I liked this section.

9. The manuscript requires improvement in linguistic quality. Several sentences have grammatical errors and structural issues that hinder readability. Before resubmission, a thorough round of professional copyediting is recommended.

10. The paper has potential; good luck in the review process!!

Response: Thank you very much for your thoughtful and constructive feedback. I appreciate your positive comments on the Results and Discussion and Implications sections.

We appreciate you again for the comments and help on the manuscript with the hope that the revisions are valuable and meet the publication of RAE.

Thank you and best regards.

Yours sincerely,
All authors